

1 High-impact low-probability events: Exposure to 2 potential large-magnitude explosive volcanic eruptions

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12 Key points

- 13 1. Approximately 312 million people live within 100 km of 136 volcanoes with potential for VEI 7
14 eruptions.
- 15 2. Laguna Caldera, Taal, and Wilis volcanoes rank highest in combined population, infrastructure,
16 and cropland exposure.
- 17 3. Exposure to tephra fall is sensitive to wind direction.

18 Key words

19 High-impact Low-probability Events, Volcanic Hazards, VEI 7 Eruptions, Exposure, Disaster Risk
20 Assessment, Resilience

21 Abstract (<250 words)

22 Due to their rarity, large-magnitude hazards are often ignored in disaster risk analysis, leaving societies with
23 unmitigated exposure and limited preparedness. Volcanic eruptions of VEI 7 magnitude occur once or
24 twice per millennium, with the last in 1815. Due to increasing populations and interdependent
25 infrastructure, such an event happening today would be catastrophic. Assessing exposure is challenging due
26 to the lack of past event data, limiting hazard modelling potential. We have developed a framework to assess
27 exposure of populations, buildings, infrastructure, and cropland to VEI 7 eruptions. We assessed exposure
28 within 100 km of 136 VEI 7 potential volcanoes, the likely extent of caldera collapse and pyroclastic density
29 currents. We find that approximately 312 million people live within 100 km of these volcanoes. Laguna
30 Caldera, Taal, and Wilis have the highest exposures. For tephra fall, we quantified exposure within isopach
31 footprints from five past VEI 7 eruptions, and rotated these around the volcano to account for wind-
32 direction variability. Among case studies, Ilopango has the highest exposure in the direction of current and
33 future wind direction, with 115 million people, 3.2 million buildings, ~4,000 km² cropland exposed. Our
34 results show that exposure is highly sensitive to wind direction and highlight the scale of potential exposure.

35 These findings can help prioritise preparation for catastrophic eruptions by integrating VEI 7 scenarios into
36 disaster risk analysis.

37 1. Introduction

38 High-impact low-probability (HILP) events are those that we have likely not prepared for. For example,
39 better preparedness for the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 CE would have likely reduced the high number
40 of global fatalities (Bollyky et al., 2022). HILP events are often excluded or underestimated in disaster risk
41 analysis, risk registers, or emergency management planning (Etkin et al., 2018; Pescaroli et al., 2025),
42 perhaps due to the rarity of these events, high mitigation costs, and a human bias towards more optimistic
43 outcomes and higher-frequency events (Lin et al., 2020; Sundh, 2024). Lin et al. (2020) terms rare, known,
44 and impactful, yet often overlooked, events as *black elephants*. With growing global populations and
45 increasing reliance on interdependent infrastructure systems, if such an extreme event were to occur, the
46 likely extent, scale, and intensity of its impacts would be considerable (Ellingwood, 2009; Fujita &
47 Yamashiki, 2022; Pescaroli et al., 2025; Royal, 2017). For some natural hazards, such as tropical cyclones or
48 extreme rainfall events, climate change amplifies the frequency and intensity of such extreme events (IPCC,
49 2023).

50 Understanding extreme natural hazard events, especially those with high impacts and low probabilities, has
51 been approached in the literature in various ways across multiple spatial scales. Statistical approaches, often
52 based on historical records, estimate the probabilities of occurrence (e.g., Burgos et al., 2022; Love, 2012;
53 Korup & Clague, 2009). Physical evidence from large-scale past events, such as sediment deposits from
54 tsunamis or floods, or tephra deposits from volcanic eruptions, can help reconstruct the magnitude and
55 recurrence of extreme events and provide constraints for probabilistic modelling (Bourrouilh-Le Jan et al.,
56 2007; De Maisonneuve & Bergal-Kuvikas, 2020; Engelhart et al., 2019). These approaches also support
57 scenario-based modelling of impacts, which has been applied to hazards such as flooding (Alfieri et al.,
58 2015; Prime et al., 2016), tsunamis (Lamarche et al., 2015; Tinti & Armigliato, 2003), and extreme weather
59 events (Trakas et al., 2019). Some studies model compound hazard scenarios, such as the effects of sea-
60 level rise together with flooding on coastal communities (Abadie et al., 2017). Counterfactual thinking of
61 past events or modelling *what-if* scenarios can help explore potential outcomes of unprecedented events
62 (Woo, 2019). For example, Lin et al. (2020) modelled the compounding effects of a potential typhoon on
63 the distribution of volcanic ash from the 1991 VEI (Volcanic Explosivity Index) 6 Pinatubo eruption in the
64 Philippines. However, large-magnitude volcanic eruptions remain underexplored in impact modelling,
65 scenario planning, and risk assessments (Newhall et al., 2018; Self, 2015).

66 Past examples of large-scale volcanic eruptions demonstrate severe global consequences. Here, we use
67 magnitude to refer to the total size of an eruption, expressed as the volume or mass of material erupted.
68 For instance, the explosive 1815 CE Tambora eruption (VEI 7) erupted $\sim 41 \text{ km}^3$ of magma (dense rock
69 equivalent—DRE; 110 km^3 pyroclastic material) and affected global climates triggering crop failures and
70 famine around the world (Crosweller et al., 2012; Kandlbauer & Sparks, 2014; Self, 2006). The explosive

71 eruption of Laacher See volcano in the East Eifel Volcanic Field, Germany, ~12,900 years ago (VEI 6),
72 potentially led to increased precipitation in Europe, damming of the Rhine river, and may have prompted
73 the migration of populations towards the southwest of Europe (Schmincke et al., 1999; Riede, 2008;
74 Donovan and Oppenheimer, 2014). Migration of populations due to volcanism was also identified from El
75 Salvador into Guatemala, due to the explosive 539 CE Ilopango eruption (VEI 7) (Donovan &
76 Oppenheimer, 2012). Non-explosive large-scale eruptions have also had widespread implications, such as
77 the formation of Large Igneous Provinces (LIPs), characterised by lava flows several kilometres thick and
78 large-scale gas emissions, which have contributed to mass extinctions (Clapham & Renne, 2019). For
79 example, the Siberian Traps LIPs, which occurred ~250 million years ago was most strongly linked to the
80 Permian mass extinction due to the gas emissions (Zhou et al., 2024). Smaller scale basaltic flood lava events
81 have also had regional effects. For example, the 1783–1784 CE effusive-explosive eruption of Lakagígar,
82 Iceland injected abundant SO₂ into the lower stratosphere, where formation of sulfate aerosols resulted in
83 cooler atmospheric temperatures and reduced rainfall, triggered increased mortality rates across Europe
84 (Wieners & Hálfðanarson, 2024; Witham & Oppenheimer, 2004). Similarly, the 937–940 CE Eldgjá
85 eruption, recently modelled with far higher sulphur emissions than previously thought, likely caused ~2 °C
86 Northern Hemisphere cooling, widespread crop failures, and famine (Fuglestad et al., 2025). These
87 examples show extreme volcanic eruptions with consequences across geographical borders and on regional,
88 hemispherical, and global scales.

89 It is difficult to model or forecast the timing, location, or scale of future large-magnitude explosive eruptions
90 and their impacts, as they are not well represented in recorded history. In fact, only ~20% of the world's
91 volcanoes with potential for an explosive eruption have records that extend further back than 10,000 years
92 ago (Huppert & Sparks, 2006). This means that global risk analysis is biased towards volcanoes with more
93 eruptions (Ward et al., 2020). In the absence of eruptive records, events can occur unexpectedly. For
94 instance, several large-magnitude eruptions have occurred at volcanoes with little or no monitoring prior
95 to the event (e.g., 2015 Calbuco; 1991 Pinatubo; 1980 Mount St. Helens). To address this, Newhall et al.
96 (2018) identified volcanoes where large-scale explosive eruptions may occur, using criteria based on record
97 of past large-scale eruptions, as well as volcano morphology and activity. This provides a basis to identify
98 areas where large-magnitude explosive eruptions may occur.

99 Today's, dense populations and complex global infrastructure mean that the consequences of a large-
100 magnitude explosive eruption could be without precedent. This raises the question: What would the impact
101 of a large-magnitude explosive eruption be today? While existing studies have assessed exposure (e.g.
102 Donovan & Oppenheimer, 2012) or infrastructure (e.g. Mani et al., 2021), they have generally done so in
103 isolation. For example, Donovan & Oppenheimer (2012) identify volcanoes with high surrounding
104 population densities using volcanoes in the Large Magnitude Explosive Volcanic Eruptions (LaMEVE)
105 database (Crosweller et al., 2012). Self (2015) qualitatively considers potential scenarios and impacts of
106 future large-scale eruptions. However, to date, no global quantitative study has systematically identified

107 locations where current exposure to population, the built environment, and agriculture, are high near
108 volcanoes with the potential for large-magnitude explosive eruptions.

109 Global quantification of exposure to volcanic activity is typically calculated within radial concentric circles
110 up to 100 km around volcanic centres to identify locations of highest exposure (e.g., Biass et al., 2024;
111 Brown et al., 2017; Ewert, 2007; Freire et al., 2019; Meredith et al., 2025; Small & Naumann, 2001). This
112 distance broadly corresponds to the average of maximum extents of life-threatening primary volcanic
113 hazards for VEI ≤ 5 eruptions (Biass et al., 2024; Ewert, 2007), based on past observations (Newhall &
114 Hoblitt, 2002). While fatalities from flow hazards have been recorded up to 100 km from volcanoes in
115 Brown et al. (2017) and modelled scenarios by Biass et al. (2024) suggest that 100 km can be considered as
116 a conservative maximum distance for pyroclastic density current (PDC) and lahar scenarios, this distance
117 may underestimate the potential maximum distance for damaging tephra fall or hazards for VEI > 5 events.
118 This calls for an updated approach to assess exposure to large-magnitude eruptions that extend beyond 100
119 km distances. Once hotspots of exposure are identified on a global level, this then can prioritise locations
120 for more localised exposure and risk analysis. Where impacts cascade through systems and networks,
121 modelling of these wider-scale effects is also important.

122 Despite growing literature on natural hazard exposure, no global study has quantified both population and
123 physical exposure to potential VEI 7 eruptions. This study addresses that gap by assessing near-field direct
124 exposure using 100 km radial buffers, and far-field direct exposure using historical tephra isopach data and
125 counterfactual scenarios. Using these approaches, we ranked *VEI 7 potential volcanoes* in terms of their human
126 population, building, infrastructure, and cropland exposure. This can be used to identify hotspots of high
127 exposure, allowing for future, targeted preparedness and planning efforts to be prioritised. We constrain
128 our assessment to VEI 7 eruptions, given the rarity of VEI 8 events and that all known VEI 7 eruptions
129 are caldera-forming, although we acknowledge that large-magnitude effusive eruptions, VEI 6, and VEI > 7
130 eruptions can also have widespread impacts. In what follows, we give a background to VEI 7 eruptions and
131 outline our methodology and data sources before presenting and discussing the findings and limitations.

132 1.1 VEI 7 eruptions

133 In this study, we constrain our assessment to VEI 7 large-magnitude explosive eruptions. These eruptions
134 are rare, occurring once or twice per millennium (Newhall et al., 2018), but extremely powerful, producing
135 bulk pyroclastic volumes of 10^2 - 10^3 km³ (Table 1) which result in kilometres-wide calderas as a consequence
136 of collapse of material into a magma reservoir. The width of a caldera generally depends on the magnitude
137 of the eruption and mass of material ejected (Branney & Acocella, 2015). These eruptions can be preceded
138 or followed by smaller magnitude eruptions and unrest.

139 Hazards associated with these eruptions result in catastrophic local direct impacts and far-reaching global
140 consequences (Kandlbauer et al., 2013; Newhall et al., 2018; Oppenheimer & Donovan, 2015; Self, 2006).
141 PDCs can extend up to 100 km from source, and high tephra plumes (> 20 km in height; Table 1) deposit

142 tephra up to and beyond 100 km (Self, 2015). Tephra fall and PDCs can directly damage and bury buildings,
 143 infrastructure, and crops, with damage and impacts changing with distance from source (Lavigne et al.,
 144 2013). These eruptions can trigger cascading hazards, such as PDCs entering water bodies and triggering
 145 tsunamis, which can greatly expand impact beyond the initial eruption site (Maeno & Imamura, 2011).
 146 These events also release vast amounts of magmatic gases which can alter climate for years, and past VEI
 147 7 events have been linked to global surface cooling and regional crop failures (Kandlbauer et al., 2013; Self,
 148 2015). Eruptions located in tropical latitudes (23.5° North to 23.5° South) tend to have broader impacts
 149 across hemispheres compared to those eruptions in polar zones (66.5° to 90° North and South; Self, 2006).

150 *Table 1: Information about the last twenty recorded eruptions in the LaMEVE database classified as VEI 7. Bulk volumes*
 151 *range from 84 km³ (Batur, Indonesia) to 320 km³ (Campi Flegrei, Italy). Blank values represent no data. Maximum*
 152 *Column Height is assumed above vent, derived from direct observations or clast-dispersal estimations (Crosweller et al., 2012)*

Volcano	Year (BP)	Bulk volume/ DRE (km ³)	PDC/Ignim brite deposit volume/ DRE (km ³)	Tephra Fall deposit volume/ DRE (km ³)	Max Column Height (km)
Tambora, Indonesia	138	110/41	5.7/18	101.3/23	33-43
Rinjani, Indonesia	693	91.25/36.5	16.8/7	7.2/3	43
Changbaishan, China/North Korea	946	100/30		100/43.5	25
Santorini, Greece	3560	123/82	72/30.64	1.2/0.24	20-36
Robeldo, Argentina	4250	110/48			
Kikai, Japan	7234	180/75	48/20	140/58	43
Crater Lake, USA	7633	120/50		20/5	55
Kurile Lake, Russia	8387	155/75	45/19.57	77/33	
Semisopochnoi, USA	9950	120/50			
Fisher, USA	10672	142/55			22
Long Island, Papua New Guinea	19278	100/40			
Zavaritzki Caldera, Russia	20000	200/80			
Ranau, Indonesia	33640	150/65			
Batur, Indonesia	34565	84/35.7	84		
Gorely, Russia	38981	120/100	120/48.98		
Campi Flegrei, Italy	39881	320/157.5	130/56.5	97/40.5	44
Kussharo, Japan	40130	170/74			
Uzon, Russia	43603	150/62.5			
Opala, Russia	44484	225/98			

153

154 2. Methodology

155 We assessed the exposure of populations and assets (buildings, infrastructure, and cropland) to VEI 7
156 eruptions (Figure 1). First, we compiled a dataset of 136 volcanoes with the potential for VEI 7 eruptions.
157 Next, we quantified populations, buildings, infrastructure, and cropland within 100 km buffers of these
158 selected volcanoes to represent exposure to PDCs and caldera formation. Finally, we used available
159 isopachs of past VEI 7 tephra fall events to quantify exposure to tephra fall for five case study examples,
160 and compared exposures for current and future wind directions. Below, we detail the steps of the
161 methodology applied in this study, also shown in Figure 1. The R code used to generate the results of this
162 study is available at: <https://github.com/elinorsmeredith/VolcExposure>.

163

164 *Figure 1: Methodology to assess exposure of populations and assets to VEI 7 eruptions. (1) Identify potential volcanoes*
165 *(Newhall et al., 2018; LaMEVE). (2) Define hazard extents for PDCs and caldera collapse (100 km buffer) and tephra*
166 *fall (rotated isopachs). (3) Quantify exposure to population, buildings, infrastructure, and cropland using recent global datasets.*
167 *(4) Normalise exposure across volcanoes and compare tephra exposure for current and future wind directions.*

168 2.1 Volcano selection

169 We compiled volcanoes that may produce a large-magnitude explosive eruption from two datasets (Figure
170 1). We selected all 120 volcanoes from the Newhall et al. (2018) dataset, which identified volcanoes active
171 in the Pleistocene and Holocene with the potential for a future VEI 7 eruption. Newhall et al. (2018) based
172 this identification on the following key criteria: 1) produced a VEI 7 eruption in the past, 2) exhibited leaks
173 of silicic magma within the last 100,000 years (particularly if in an arcuate volcanic cluster), 3) are large and
174 mature stratovolcanoes (mostly exceeding 200 km³ in volume), 4) are volcanic complexes believed to be
175 underlain by substantial magma reservoirs and showing recent signs of unrest, 5) have extensional tectonics

176 and high magma supply rate, and/or 6) have probable excess magmatic gas accumulation. They exclude
177 most volcanoes where the latest VEI 7 eruption occurred more than one million years ago, unless they
178 show evidence of younger activity. Newhall et al. (2018) note that none of these volcanoes are expected to
179 produce a VEI 7 eruption in the next millennium. For a more conservative dataset, we also included 16
180 volcanoes that have produced eruptions of M 6.5 – 7.5 in the past, listed in the LaMEVE database
181 (Croweller et al., 2012) that are not included within the Newhall et al. (2018) dataset.

182 In our final combined dataset, we added the latitude and longitude coordinates of each volcano, and the
183 country, region, and continent where the volcano is located, based on data from the Volcanoes of the World
184 (VOTW) v. 5.2.8 database (Global Volcanism Program, 2025) database. The database places coordinates at
185 the summit for volcanoes with a distinct primary edifice, or close to known vents. For volcanic fields with
186 multiple vents, the location corresponds to the most prominent or active vent, the most recently erupting
187 vent, or the centre of the field, depending on available information (Global Volcanism Program, 2025).
188 This resulted in a dataset of 136 volcanoes; from here we refer to these as *VEI 7 potential volcanoes*.

189 2.2 Exposure data

190 In this study, we compiled exposure data from four different datasets (Figure 1). We used population data
191 from the 100-m resolution 2020 Global Human Settlement (GHS-POP) raster (Schiavina et al., 2023). Each
192 pixel represents the estimated number of people living within that grid cell, derived from satellite imagery.
193 We selected this dataset over alternatives to focus on where people live, rather than transient or ambient
194 population patterns. For the PDC and caldera collapse exposure, we used 39 critical infrastructure rasters
195 (each at 0.10° resolution) from Nirandjan et al. (2022), which each give infrastructure density derived from
196 OpenStreetMap (OSM) data collected in 2020. For the tephra fall exposure analysis we used the 0.10 degree
197 resolution Community Infrastructure and Services Index (CISI) raster from Nirandjan et al. (2022). The
198 CISI is a composite and normalised global measure of all 39 types of critical infrastructure. The raster gives
199 a normalised value of each pixel, where a pixel of 0 represents no infrastructure and 1 represents highest
200 density relative to the other cells. For the 100 km buffers we normalised values from the 39 individual
201 infrastructure rasters across the full set of 136 volcanoes, to enable relative ranking. For the tephra fall case
202 studies, we extracted exposure directly from the composite CISI index raster, since the analysis focused on
203 absolute exposure within individual isopachs rather than volcano comparison. For cropland, we used the
204 pixels classified as cropland in the 100-m resolution 2019 Copernicus Global Land Cover v3 raster (CGLS-
205 LC100; Buchhorn et al., 2020) to capture the area of cropland exposed. Finally, we downloaded
206 OpenStreetMap building footprints, in May 2025, to calculate building density.

207 2.3 Pyroclastic density current and caldera collapse hazard analysis

208 The focus of our study is on the primary hazards of VEI 7 eruptions: PDCs, caldera collapse, and tephra
209 fall. To assess exposure to PDCs and caldera collapse, we mapped the locations of the compiled *VEI 7*
210 *potential volcanoes* dataset of 136 volcanoes (Figure 1). We created 100 km radial geodesic buffers around each

211 volcano point to represent the maximum extent of caldera collapse and PDC runout. We projected all layers
212 to a consistent World Mollweide projection (EPSG:54009) to match the population raster. We extracted
213 exposure values from population and 39 infrastructure rasters using the *ExactExtract* package in R. This
214 package performs zonal statistics by summing raster values within each buffer, weighting pixels by their
215 fractional overlap to account for partial coverage. For infrastructure we created our own CISI values
216 normalised across the 136 volcanoes, where pixel values of 1 and 0 relate to the highest and lowest level of
217 exposure, respectively, across the 100-km buffers. We calculated the number of buildings by counting
218 building footprints that intersected each buffer. We calculated cropland exposure in Google Earth Engine
219 by extracting the area of pixels classified as cropland (land cover class 40) within each buffer. If volcanoes
220 are close together and 100-km buffers overlap, the exposures may be double counted across the dataset.

221 To identify eruptions with tsunami potential, we overlaid the Natural Earth (2024) 1:10m coastline dataset
222 and identified *VEI 7 potential volcanoes* whose 100 km radius intersected the coastline. Additionally, we
223 highlighted the latitude of each volcano to categorise the eruption by the scale of potential climate impacts.
224 We also indicated whether the 100 km buffer intersected multiple countries of the Natural Earth (2024)
225 1:10m countries outline, highlighting cross-border exposure of direct hazards.

226 2.4 Volcano Rankings

227 Once we had exposure calculations for 100 km buffers around the 136 *VEI 7 potential volcanoes*, we created
228 an index to compare and rank the volcanoes. We normalised the quantities of population, infrastructure,
229 buildings, and cropland to an index out of 10, where zero represents no exposure, and 10 represents the
230 maximum amount of exposure across the 136 volcanoes. We then ranked the volcanoes by each exposure
231 type, with rank 1 as the normalised value of 1, and rank 136 as the normalised value of 0. Finally, we
232 calculated an average rank across all four exposure type ranks, essentially treating each exposure type with
233 equal weight.

234 In order to identify volcanoes with limited attention or research coverage, we also ranked volcanoes by the
235 number of recent published peer-reviewed studies. We used the framework and code of Lerner et al. (2023)
236 as a basis for our methodology to download and assess literature metadata. We identified English-language
237 published research articles on volcanoes by searching the Web of Science database of published literature
238 using the terminology “volcan*”. We recognise that this methodology does not include studies in non-
239 English languages. From this list we downloaded the metadata of the most recent 100,000 articles, in July
240 2025, which extended back to 2020. We matched the name of the *VEI 7 potential volcano* with any volcano
241 name mentioned in the article titles, and summed the number of articles for each volcano. We based this
242 on the spelling used in the Global Volcanism Programme list of Holocene volcanoes (GVP, 2024). We then
243 ranked the volcanoes based on the maximum number of articles for a volcano. Through the exposure
244 ranking and the research ranking, we can identify areas of concern; where there are volcanoes with high
245 exposure, but seemingly little research conducted.

246 2.5 Tephra fall hazard analysis

247 To assess the extent and exposure of tephra fall hazard from VEI 7 eruptions, we compiled published
248 isopachs of past VEI 7 eruptions. We only included isopachs of final tephra deposits (i.e., not of different
249 eruptive phases). We used available isopachs for 946 CE Changbaishan, China, and georeferenced and
250 digitised the isopachs of an additional five past VEI 7 eruptions, all listed in Table 2.

251 We selected case studies with available isopachs with tephra thickness of ≥ 5 cm. This threshold was chosen
252 because ash accumulation at or above this level is linked to a high likelihood of damage to power, water,
253 transport, and communication infrastructure, and an increased risk of roof collapse (Wilson et al., 2012).
254 Isopachs were projected to World Mollweide projection (EPSG:54009) to match the exposure datasets. For
255 the ≥ 5 cm isopach, we measured the maximum deposit extent, defined by the longest distance across the
256 isopach, and isopach area, in order to compare tephra fall deposit distribution from the volcano. To explore
257 the influence of isopach area, we calculated the area of each isopach intervals available (e.g., 2–5 cm, 5–10
258 cm, >10 cm) and extracted populations within these intervals, using the dataset and extraction
259 methodologies of Sections 2.2 and 2.3. As Fisher volcano, USA, did not have any population exposure, we
260 excluded it from the rest of the analysis. This resulted in a dataset of five case studies. For each case study
261 isopach, we then divided the population by area for each tephra thickness interval to calculate population
262 density exposed to tephra thicknesses.

263 To assess the exposure under varying wind directions, we rotated the isopach around each volcano in 16-
264 point (22.5 degree) intervals starting from north. At each interval, we calculated exposure of populations,
265 buildings, infrastructure, and cropland from the datasets and extraction methodologies in Section 2.2 and
266 Section 2.3. For the infrastructure score, we extracted and summed values from the 39 critical infrastructure
267 rasters, detailed in Section 2.2, and normalised these across the direction intervals. We then identified
268 exposures for the direction of the past event, as well as exposures in the directions of maximum and
269 minimum exposure quantities for each exposure types.

270 We also highlighted exposures in the direction of current and future predominant winds, derived from 10-
271 year 6-hourly mean reanalysis data (2014-2024) from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather
272 Forecasts Reanalysis v5 (ECMWF ERA-5) dataset (Hersbach et al., 2023), and 10-year monthly-mean future
273 wind data (2090-2100) from the UK Earth System Model (UKESM1.1). Projected wind data were extracted
274 from the UKESM1.1 simulations with three ensemble members under the SSP3-7.0 Shared Socioeconomic
275 Pathway, a high future anthropogenic warming scenario (Mulcahy et al., 2023).

276 To determine current and future wind directions, we first extracted wind data from the nearest grid in the
277 ERA-5 dataset ($0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ resolution) and UKESM1.1 simulations ($1.25^\circ \times 1.875^\circ$ resolution) to the
278 volcano location. We then averaged wind directions across heights likely to experience the bulk of tephra
279 release from the umbrella cloud of the volcanic plume (between 56 and 84 % of the maximum plume

280 height; following the concept of the neutral buoyancy region described by Bonadonna & Phillips, 2003;
 281 S2). Maximum plume heights were taken from the recorded plume height of the past eruption, if known
 282 (Table 2), and Kurile was inferred. We determined the current and future predominant wind directions at
 283 the volcano based on the frequency of the vertically averaged wind direction.

284 *Table 2: Case study VEI 7 eruptions used in this study, the reference for the isopach used, and maximum plume heights*
 285 *recorded. The maximum plume heights are assumed to be above sea level (asl) unless stated above the volcano. Blank values*
 286 *represent no data. For Kurile, an inferred height of 31km was used.*

Eruption	Isopach Reference	Maximum Plume Height (km)	Height Reference
1815 CE Tambora, Indonesia	Sigurdsson and Carey, 1989	43 (above the volcano)	Sigurdsson and Carey, 1989
946 CE Changbaishan, China	Yang et al., 2021	~25	Horne and Schmincke, 2000
450 CE Ilopango, El Salvador	Dull et al., 2018	31	LaMEVE database
10,672 BP Fisher, USA	Stelling et al., 2005	22	Gardner et al., 2007
1257 CE Rinjani, Indonesia	Vidal et al., 2016	43	Vidal et al., 2016
8,387 BP Kurile, Russia	Ponomareva et al., 2004	31	

287

288 3 Results

289 We present our results below in two parts; firstly, we give the *VEI 7 potential volcanoes* rankings based on
 290 exposure within 100-km distances, and secondly, we present exposure to tephra fall based on past VEI 7
 291 isopach examples. The results for all our exposure analyses are available in Section 8 Data Availability.

292 3.1 Global distribution of potential VEI 7 eruptions

293 The Global Volcanism Program (2025) identifies 2,640 volcanoes that have had Pleistocene or Holocene
 294 eruptions. Of these, we considered that 5 % (136 volcanoes) could have the potential to produce a VEI 7
 295 eruption (Figure 2). Some 81 % (110 volcanoes) have record of a past VEI 7 eruption. Based on Figure 2B;
 296 East Asia, Southeast Asia, and Oceania have the highest number of volcanoes with the potential for VEI 7
 297 eruptions, and every identified volcano in East Asia has record of a past VEI 7 event. Regions such as the
 298 Middle East, and Africa show comparatively lower counts. For other regions, such as the Caribbean or
 299 Northern Europe, no *VEI 7 potential volcanoes* have been identified.

300

301 **Figure 2:** The distribution and regional frequency of volcanoes with the potential for a future VEI 7 eruption, shown as A)
 302 a global map with regions indicated as circles. Red triangles highlight volcanoes with a prior VEI 7 eruption, while grey
 303 triangles represent those without. B) A bar chart showing the number of VEI 7 potential volcanoes per region, categorised by
 304 the presence (red) or absence (grey) of a prior VEI 7 eruption.

305 3.2 Global exposure to VEI 7 caldera collapse and pyroclastic density currents

306 The top-ranked volcano in terms of exposure across all four exposure types is Laguna Caldera in the
 307 Philippines, followed closely by Taal in the Philippines and Wilis in Indonesia (Table 3). The 30 highest-
 308 ranked *VEI 7 potential volcanoes* are primarily located in East and Southeast Asia, Central America, and the
 309 Middle East (Figure 3; Table 3). Many are within close proximity to large urban areas such as Manila, Naples,
 310 Tokyo, and Guatemala City. Areas with high population typically also show higher amounts of
 311 infrastructure and buildings (Figure 3), and lower exposure to cropland. However, Wilis volcano and
 312 volcanoes in East Africa shows high levels of both cropland and population exposure. Many volcanoes
 313 located in Russia, Antarctica, and North America (Alaska) are ranked low across all exposure types (dark
 314 purple in Figure 3A), and located away from populations and assets.

315 In total, there are 312,197,500 people living within 100 km of a *VEI 7 potential volcano*, with major exposed
 316 population clusters in Southeast Asia, East Africa, and Central America (Figure 3B). Laguna Caldera in the
 317 Philippines (n=34,548,228) has the most people living within 100 km (Figure 3B; Table 3), encompassing
 318 large parts of the capital city, Manila. *VEI 7 potential volcanoes* with no populations exposed are at Young
 319 Island, off the coast of Antarctica, and Semisopchnoi, in the Aleutian Islands of Alaska.

320 The most buildings (n=4,275,640) and infrastructure (score of 19) are located around Usami volcano in
 321 Japan (Figure 3D-E; Table 3). High infrastructure is noted in Oceania, primarily New Zealand, and parts
 322 of North America, despite lower levels of other exposure types (Figure 3E). More cropland is exposed at
 323 volcanoes in East Africa, the Middle East, and Central America. Almost 22,000 km² of cropland is exposed
 324 to Gademota Caldera (Figure 3C), located in Ethiopia, a fertile area identified in past studies as showing
 325 rapid expansion of cultivation on volcanic soils (Rembold et al., 2000). Despite its high ranking for
 326 population (rank 12) and cropland (rank 1), the lower rankings for infrastructure (rank 84) and buildings
 327 (rank 67), result in an overall rank of 36 for Gademota volcano.

328 Several volcanoes, such as Pacaya, Ilopango, and Aragats are located in regions where direct VEI 7 eruption
 329 impacts would likely cross multiple national borders (Table 3). In terms of indirect hazards, half (n=15) of
 330 the top 30 ranked volcanoes are located in the tropical zone (23.5° North to 23.5° South) across Southeast
 331 Asia, East Africa, and Central America, where a VEI 7 eruption would likely affect both hemispheres (Table
 332 3). A smaller number are located in the Temperate Zones (35° to 66.5° North and South), including several
 333 Italian and Japanese volcanoes (Figure 3A).

334

335 **Figure 3:** Global maps showing the location of the 136 VEI7 potential volcanoes. A) Volcanoes are coloured the rank of
 336 combined exposure to population, buildings, infrastructure, and cropland (equally weighted). Higher ranks (light blue) indicate
 337 more exposure and lower ranks (dark purple) indicate less exposure. B-E) Volcanoes are coloured by absolute values of
 338 exposure within 100 km of B) population, C) cropland, D) buildings, and E) infrastructure score. Volcanoes with the highest
 339 exposure for each category are labelled.

340 Table 3: Top 30 out of 136 VEI7 potential volcanoes ranked by exposure. The rank for each exposure type are shown. If
 341 the 100 km buffer for the volcano overlaps multiple islands or countries, or coastline/s, these are indicated. C.I. stands for
 342 critical infrastructure.

Rank	Volcano	Average Rank	Population Rank	C.I. Rank	Buildings Rank	Cropland Rank	Direct Scale		Indirect scale	
							Multiple countries?	Tsunami potential y/n	Climate latitude	
1	Laguna Caldera, Philippines	11	1	2	2	39		Yes	Tropical	
2	Taal, Philippines	14	2	5	3	46		Yes	Tropical	
3	Wilis, Indonesia	17.75	5	50	6	10		Yes	Tropical	
4	Tengger Caldera, Indonesia	20.25	3	36	16	26		Yes	Tropical	
5	Sabatini Complex, Italy	20.75	33	3	19	28		Yes	Temperate	
6	Colli Albani, Italy	22.25	28	4	21	36		Yes	Temperate	
7	Vulsini, Italy	22.5	36	6	25	23		Yes	Temperate	
8	Atitlán, Guatemala	24.25	13	58	8	18		Yes	Tropical	
9	Usami, Japan	25	4	1	1	94		Yes	Temperate	
10	Pacaya, Guatemala	25.5	16	59	14	13	Yes: Guatemala, El Salvador	Yes	Tropical	
11	Futamata, Japan	27.75	38	9	17	47		Yes	Temperate	
12	Asosan, Japan	28	20	11	12	69		Yes	Temperate	
13	Kujusan, Japan	29	18	10	13	75		Yes	Temperate	
14	Yufu-Tsurumi, Japan	29.25	17	8	15	77		Yes	Temperate	
15	Menengai, Kenya	31.25	30	80	7	8		No	Tropical	
16	Coatepeque Caldera, El Salvador	32.25	22	61	32	14	Yes: El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras	Yes	Tropical	
17	Campi Flegrei, Italy	32.75	29	21	38	43		Yes	Temperate	
18	Acoculco, Mexico	33.25	14	24	80	15		Yes	Tropical	
19	Damavand, Iran	33.25	10	12	77	34		Yes	Temperate	
20	Akita-Yakeyama, Japan	33.75	56	13	18	48		Yes	Temperate	
21	Apaneca Range, El Salvador	34.25	26	62	33	16	Yes: El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras	Yes	Tropical	
22	Iyang-Argapura, Indonesia	34.5	11	69	26	32		Yes	Tropical	
23	Ilopango, El Salvador	35.5	25	63	37	17	Yes: El Salvador, Honduras	Yes	Tropical	
24	Kamitakara, Japan	36	37	14	23	70		Yes	Temperate	
25	Momisawadake, Japan	36.5	39	15	20	72		Yes	Temperate	
26	Humeros, Los, Mexico	37.5	19	35	84	12		Yes	Tropical	
27	Aragats, Armenia	38.5	55	27	48	24	Yes: Georgia, Zerbaijan, Turkey, Armenia	No	Temperate	
28	Shala, Ethiopia	38.75	7	89	55	4		No	Tropical	
29	Corbetti Caldera, Ethiopia	39	6	90	54	6		Yes	Tropical	
30	Hodaka-dake, Japan	39	43	16	24	73		Yes	Temperate	

343 3.2 Exposure and research rankings

344 Figure 4 highlights which VEI 7 potential volcanoes appear to receive less research attention, based on the
 345 number of studies published in the last 100,000 papers indexed in the Web of Science. Several volcanoes
 346 with a high exposure rank have relatively few studies, highlighted in the bottom right of the matrix in Figure
 347 4, such as Wilis, Laguna Caldera, Atitlán, Usami, and Yufu-Tsurumi. However, Taal volcano is ranked

348 highly for exposure and also has a relatively high number of recent studies (n=72). Other volcanoes such
 349 as Taupo, Changbaishan, Santorini, Yellowstone, and Uzon volcanoes have over 100 studies each, yet have
 350 relatively lower exposure rankings of over 100. This points to a mismatch between exposure and research
 351 effort (as defined in Sect. 2.4), particularly across parts of East Africa, Southeast Asia, and Central America.

352
 353 **Figure 4:** Matrix showing the VEI 7 potential volcanoes in relation to their average exposure rank across the exposure
 354 types (population, buildings, infrastructure, and cropland) and the number of studies on the volcano. The number of studies is
 355 based on the last 100,000 papers indexed within the Web of Science inventory (encompassing January 2020 – July 2025).
 356 The bottom right highlights key volcanoes where there are a lack of studies but high exposure. Volcanoes without any studies
 357 are not shown, include Wilis with average exposure rank of three, and Kujusan, Futamata, and Asosan with average exposure
 358 ranks between 20 – 30, and 44 volcanoes with exposure ranks between 30 and 136.

359 3.3 Exposure to VEI 7 tephra fall

360 Tephra fall from past VEI 7 eruptions extended far beyond 100 km from each volcano. The farthest tephra
 361 fall out of the key case studies is at Kurile where tephra reached a thickness of 5 cm at a distance of ~1,330
 362 km from the volcano.

363 Tephra falls extended over multiple islands or countries, and over areas of current high population density.
 364 For example, isopachs from the Tambora eruption in the Sunda Arc extend across Java, Bali, Lombok,

365 Sumbawa, and into Kalimantan and Sulawesi. The city of Denpasar on the island of Bali is located within
 366 both the 5 cm isopach of the Rinjani eruption and the 20 cm isopach of the Tambora eruption (Figures 5A
 367 and 5C). The Ilopango eruption presented widespread tephra distribution across Central America, with
 368 deposits covering parts of Guatemala, Honduras, and Nicaragua, as well as the entirety of El Salvador. The
 369 capital of El Salvador, San Salvador, lies within a deposit thickness exceeding 100 cm (Figure 5B). In Japan,
 370 the Changbaishan isopachs cover the cities of Sapporo (2 cm) and Aomori (5 cm). In Russia, Vladivostok
 371 lies within the 10 cm isopach band from the Changbaishan isopach (Figure 5D), and Magadan falls within
 372 the 5 cm isopach of the Kurile isopach (Figure 5E).

373

374 **Figure 5:** Past VEI 7 tephra isopachs overlaying current population maps for case study events: A) Tambora (Sigurdsson
 375 and Carey, 1989); B) Ilopango (Dull et al., 2018); C) Rinjani (Vidal et al., 2016); D) Changbaishan (Yang et al.,
 376 2021); and E) Kurile (Ponomareva et al., 2004). The Changbaishan 1-cm isopach is constructed with very limited
 377 observations as constraints. Tephra extents are shown as black lines and thickness in cm is labelled. Dashed lines show

378 *distances inferred by the authors. Bold text highlights the key island and country names, and italic text highlights key urban*
 379 *areas. The colours on the map show the population density, with dark blue as highly dense areas. The area of the 5-cm isopach*
 380 *and the distance of the farthest extent of 5 cm is indicated, ranging from 220 km (Rinjani) to 1,330 km (Kurile). The Fisher*
 381 *eruption is not shown as there is no population exposure.*

382 Populations exposed to thinner deposits (≤ 10 cm) exceed 12 million people in two cases (Figure 6; S1),
 383 while less than ~ 6 million people are exposed to thicker deposits (>30 cm) because they affect smaller
 384 areas and expose far fewer people (Figure 6A). For some examples, such as Ilopango and Rinjani, dense
 385 concentrations of people are located relatively close to the volcano with the largest exposed population
 386 densities (>500 people/km²) lying within the >30 cm isopach (Figure 6B).

387

388 **Figure 6:** Heatmaps coloured by A) absolute numbers of population and B) population density within the area of each
 389 tephra thickness band of the isopachs. Some lower thicknesses are missing from the isopachs shown as gaps at the bottom of
 390 the plot, and the upper band of tephra thickness for each volcano is represented as a gradient of transparency as there is no
 391 upper thickness limit recorded. This highlights the variability of exposure with isopach area. Where there are high levels of
 392 population density at Rinjani, there are relatively low absolute values of population compared to Tambora, and vice versa,
 393 where high absolute values of population for Tambora align with relatively lower population densities at Rinjani. Volcanoes
 394 are ordered by highest to lowest 5cm tephra isopach area.

395 The case studies demonstrate the wide variability in exposure patterns. Across all case studies, Ilopango
 396 shows highest amounts of exposure in the direction of current wind directions, except for Changbaishan
 397 with highest levels of infrastructure exposed (Figure 7). However, small changes in wind direction
 398 substantially alter exposure footprints for population, buildings, cropland, and infrastructure (Figure 7). For
 399 example, population exposure at Ilopango increases by 13.9 % between the past eruption direction and
 400 current wind directions (Figure 7; Table 5). Ilopango presents the highest exposure under current or future
 401 wind directions (W), with over 131 million people and ~ 4 million buildings exposed (Figure 7; Table 5).
 402 Also, cropland exposure at Ilopango almost doubles from $\sim 26,250$ km² in the past eruption direction (SE)
 403 to $\sim 40,448$ km² in the current and future wind direction. For Tambora, population exposure drops ~ 6.8
 404 million, from ~ 39.4 in the direction of the past eruption, to 32.9 million in the current and future

405 predominant wind direction. Shifts in wind direction, shown as past, current, and future wind directions,
406 result in substantial increases or decreases in exposure.

407 The case studies show variability in exposures across different volcanic settings, isopach areas, and wind
408 variability. In the following section, we discuss the implications of these findings.

409

410 **Figure 7:** Rose diagrams for five case study eruptions showing exposure of population (yellow), cropland (green), buildings
 411 (blue), and infrastructure (orange). The black line denotes the direction of tephra dispersion from the last known VEI 7
 412 eruption, while the black and grey arrows indicate the present and future prevailing wind directions (in the direction of blowing

413 towards the purple), respectively. The light grey bars next to the grey arrow show the uncertainty of the future wind direction
 414 based on the ensemble results. Note the y axis for each of the exposures are different scales, therefore cannot be directly compared.
 415 Values are summarised in Table 5.

416 **Table 5:** Table of the exposure to >5 cm of tephra fall for five case study VEI 7 eruptions. Exposures are given for four
 417 exposure types, and calculated by the isopach in the direction of the past eruption, the current predominant wind direction, and
 418 future wind direction for 2100. The highest exposure for each volcano and exposure type is highlighted. C.I. stands for critical
 419 infrastructure, which is given as a calculated infrastructure score. All values rounded to nearest integer.

Volcano	Exposure type	Past eruption direction	Current/future predominant wind direction
Tambora	Population	39,390,504	32,572,027
	Buildings	5,755,421	5,092,985
	C.I.	11	9
	Cropland (km)	22,425	16,102
Rinjani	Population	24,450,440	24,450,440
	Buildings	2,534,161	2,534,161
	C.I.	7	7
	Cropland (km)	1,400	1,400
Kurile	Population	125,533	828,120
	Buildings	12,042	2,638,845
	C.I.	1	5
	Cropland (km)	77	172
Changbaishan	Population	17,057,586	17,057,586
	Buildings	1,009,374	1,009,374
	C.I.	60	60
	Cropland (km)	0.005	0.005
Ilopango	Population	74,075,983	115,160,021
	Buildings	2,084,437	3,808,598
	C.I.	31	47
	Cropland (km)	26,250	40,448

420

421 4 Discussion

422 This global study quantifies direct exposure to VEI 7 eruptions, revealing East and Southeast Asia as key
 423 locations of *VEI 7 potential volcanoes* (Figure 2), due to high volcano density and record of past large-
 424 magnitude eruptions. We use the Newhall et al. (2018) dataset to identify potential VEI 7 sources beyond
 425 those with confirmed past events. However, many volcanoes have a lack of detailed eruption histories
 426 (Burgos et al., 2022). Remote, submarine, or poorly studied volcanoes are thus likely underrepresented in
 427 our dataset of potential VEI7 eruptions due to these data gaps. While the occurrence of past VEI 7
 428 eruptions provides important precedent, there may be volcanoes that have no evidence (observed or actual)

429 of a VEI 7 eruption such that future events may occur at volcanoes not in our dataset. Therefore, the global
430 exposure to potential VEI 7 eruptions is still likely underestimated in our dataset.

431 Direct exposure to a potential VEI 7 eruption is substantial, with over 300 million people residing within
432 100 km of *VEI 7 potential volcanoes*. Laguna Caldera and Taal in the Philippines, and Wilis in Indonesia, rank
433 highest across all exposure types. This aligns with findings from Burgos et al. (2022), who identified Laguna
434 Caldera as a potentially active volcano with particularly high population exposure. The close proximity of
435 Manila to both Taal and Laguna Caldera is reflected in our exposure rankings, and has been previously
436 highlighted by Donovan and Oppenheimer (2012), who identified Manila as a major city exposed to large-
437 magnitude explosive eruptions. Impacts to cities, as major economic and political hubs, would likely have
438 cascading impacts on national and regional scales (Meredith et al., 2025). Therefore, the close proximity of
439 cities to volcanoes and exposed to VEI 7 eruptions provides major challenges for emergency planning,
440 evacuation and response (Calderon Barraza, 2024).

441 Exposure differs greatly regionally and between volcanoes, depending on local geography, land use, and
442 population distribution. Volcanoes close to urban areas are reflected in high building and infrastructure
443 exposure, such as at Usami volcano in Japan (Figure 3D-E). While other areas, such as around Gademota
444 Caldera in Ethiopia, have high levels of cropland exposed, indicating risks to livelihoods and rural
445 communities. Around Wilis volcano, forests have been cleared for cropland and communities are
446 dependent on agriculture (Amanah et al., 2017; Erlinawati et al., 2010). In Central America, Ilopango
447 Caldera displays high levels of both cropland and population exposure. This suggests that at Ilopango and
448 Wilis volcanoes, eruptions would disrupt both rural livelihoods and highly populated settlements. These
449 examples highlight that exposure metrics need to capture more than just raw population counts, to reflect
450 exposure typologies or vulnerabilities. This approach helps to prioritise and design equitable preparedness
451 strategies tailored to the local communities.

452 Different volcanic hazards from a VEI 7 eruption produce varying spatial reach and exposure. At the
453 eruption site, we anticipate complete destruction of exposed assets due to caldera collapse and PDCs, which
454 have resulted in the permanent abandonment of settlements, such as at Taupō (~232 CE) and Tambora
455 (1815) (Calderon Barraza, 2024). Archaeological investigations reveal settlements buried under thick
456 material from the 1257 Rinjani eruption extending across Lombok island, within 100 km of the volcano
457 (Lavigne et al., 2013). In contrast, tephra fall, while more widespread, would be less destructive far-field
458 from the volcano. Thicknesses of 5 cm or more can damage critical infrastructure and cause roof collapse
459 of certain building types (Wilson et al., 2012), while ~0.5 - 4 cm equivalent thickness (5 - 40 kg/m²) can
460 cause substantial crop production decline, depending on ash properties and plant traits (Ligot et al., 2023).
461 Even moderate thickness (10 - 30 cm) zones can expose very large populations if they intersect dense
462 settlements (Figure 6; S1) or affect extensive cropland in rural areas. This contrast is a challenge for
463 preparedness strategies; while tephra has higher exposure, its impacts are, on average, less severe and

464 recoverable, whereas PDCs and caldera collapse are highly destructive but are focused within the 100 km
465 buffer. Effective planning for such scenarios needs to balance both the scale, duration, and intensity of the
466 hazard.

467 Restricting the assessment of direct impacts to 100 km underestimates the potential impact of VEI 7
468 eruptions. In our Tambora dataset, the exposed population within the past 5-cm tephra footprint (~39
469 million) far exceeds the population located within the 100-km radial buffer (~1 million), because the distal
470 footprint intersects highly-dense areas of Java and Bali islands, whereas the 100-km buffer lies largely on
471 sparsely populated Sumbawa island. Raffles (1816) noted, after the Tambora eruption, loss of cropland and
472 livestock by ashfall in Banyuwangi, Indonesia, ~400 km away from the volcano. We propose that the 100
473 km buffers are used to identify large-scale destruction from VEI 7 eruptions, and our scenario-based
474 isopach methodology can be used to account for far-field exposure to tephra fall, accounting for wind
475 directions and isopach extent. By calculating population densities within each tephra thickness footprint, as
476 shown in Figure 7, we can distinguish between hazards that affect many people over a large area, and those
477 that affect highly dense populations in smaller areas. Tephra isopachs from past eruptions could be applied
478 to volcanoes of similar latitude, making the broad assumption that they experience comparable wind speeds
479 (influencing the isopach shape), to quantify exposure where there are no past VEI 7 deposits and/or
480 isopachs available.

481 Wind direction is a critical driver of far-field tephra exposure, with small directional shifts producing large
482 changes in exposed populations and assets. Figures 6 and 7 highlight how downwind tephra dispersion and
483 deposit area influence total quantities of exposure. Larger isopach areas increase the likelihood of
484 intersecting populated or cultivated areas, while smaller footprints can still result in high exposure if they
485 overlap densely populated areas (Figure 6). Where the tephra isopach coincides with a dense urban area or
486 a large quantity of cropland, the exposure increases relative to the other directions (Figure 7). Building on
487 this, future changes in wind patterns under different climatic scenarios increase the likelihood of winds
488 blowing towards certain regions (Figure 7). Simply overlaying past tephra fall isopachs onto current
489 exposure maps does not account for atypical past wind conditions at the time of eruption or changes in
490 predominant wind directions since that eruption, potentially underestimating or overestimating exposure.

491 VEI 7 eruptions are often overlooked, likely due to their rarity and high preparedness costs. Several highly
492 exposed volcanoes have limited academic attention (Figure 4), indicating possible gaps in hazard awareness.
493 The preparedness for and public understanding of VEI 7 eruptions remains limited in many regions
494 (Donovan & Oppenheimer, 2012), likely because preparing for such events is difficult due to the need to
495 weigh the substantial economic and social costs of large-scale evacuations and mitigation efforts against the
496 potentially catastrophic impacts of inaction. The low probability of a VEI 7 eruption can lead to a tendency
497 to downplay the risk and defer costly preparedness measures. However, prioritising high-impact events
498 despite low probability, as considered in assessments of other hazards such as flooding (Merz et al., 2009),

499 can reduce catastrophic losses, justifying long-term resilience investments, such as strengthening
500 infrastructure and developing evacuation plans. Accounting for this societal risk perception can strengthen
501 the justification for investing in mitigation strategies targeting extreme events (Tyszka, 2017), particularly
502 as individuals tend to underprepare for low-probability hazards (Royal, 2017).

503 VEI 7 hazards often cross-national borders, raising challenges for data sharing, joint preparedness planning,
504 and coordinating large-scale responses. Few existing frameworks address the complexities of cross-border
505 volcanic hazards (Donovan & Oppenheimer, 2019) and the lack of recent experience with VEI 7 eruptions
506 can make it difficult to convey the potential severity of the threat and the necessity of preparedness.
507 Effective communication about extreme volcanic risk must be built in advance before a crisis arises
508 (Donovan and Oppenheimer, 2017). Where probabilistic hazard maps are not feasible for VEI >6
509 eruptions, worst-case scenario exposure assessments, such as provided in this study, can support informed
510 decision making (Doyle et al., 2014), and applying risk aversion functions to decision-making models can
511 help prioritise extreme, low-probability events that might otherwise be neglected (Tyszka, 2017; Fujita and
512 Yamashiki, 2022; Ellingwood, 2009). Other tools such as localised thought experiments and counterfactual
513 analyses (e.g., Lin et al. 2020) could help unravel the complexities involved in planning for such HILP
514 scenarios across national borders. International cooperation, communication, and scenario planning are
515 essential to manage the transboundary risks of VEI 7 eruptions.

516 Whilst the scale of exposure is high, the capacity to respond varies considerably across volcanic settings,
517 likely influenced by eruption history, required resources, and also authority and community experiences and
518 perceptions. For instance, local populations around the highly exposed and monitored Taal volcano have
519 recent experience with smaller (VEI <5) eruptions, this is not the case for communities near Wilis volcano,
520 with no confirmed historical eruptions or active monitoring. As noted by Amanah et al. (2017), the
521 perception of dormancy among local communities may be misleading, and their capacity to respond to a
522 large eruption of Wilis volcano is limited. While a VEI 7 event would likely be preceded by some smaller
523 eruptions or unrest (Calderon Barraza, 2024), there is a risk of overlooking seemingly inactive volcanoes
524 despite high exposure, particularly where historical records are sparse and preparedness is low.

525 5 Future work

526 5.1 Indirect hazards

527 Our approach focused on exposure to direct hazards, although there is high potential for cascading hazards
528 and impacts extending the effects beyond the hazard footprints. Past VEI 7 eruptions have triggered
529 cascades of secondary hazards, including tsunamis, lahars, and global climatic effects from stratospheric
530 aerosol injection, extending the exposure far beyond 100 km and amplifying their global impact. Caldera
531 collapse, PDCs entering the sea, and/or volcanic flank failure (e.g., 1883 and 2018 Krakatoa: Heidarzadeh
532 et al., 2020, Francis, 1985; 1792 Unzen: Miyamoto, 2010; 1630–1550 B.C. Santorini: Goodman-Tchernov
533 et al., 2009) can generate tsunamis. As the majority (n=? x%) of the volcanoes in our dataset are located

534 within 100 km of a coastline, there is potential for tsunami generation and far-field effects. Localised
535 assessment using scenarios of tsunami generation can help further estimate exposure to these eruptions.

536 Given that the majority of the VEI 7 candidate volcanoes in our dataset are located in tropical latitudes, the
537 likelihood of widespread climate effects is elevated. Recent ensemble modelling shows that extremely large
538 eruptions (e.g., 40 Tg sulphur injections) can induce extreme climatic anomalies, with eruption latitude
539 influencing global impacts, which can last for up to three years post-eruption (Freychet et al., 2023). For
540 example, observations after the 2022 Hunga Tonga–Hunga Ha‘apai eruption (VEI 5) show up to 4 °C of
541 stratospheric cooling in 2023 (Stocker et al., 2024). Notably, tropical eruptions are associated with
542 heightened risk of multi-regional droughts and monsoon disruptions, particularly across key agricultural
543 zones (Freychet et al., 2023). These eruptions unfold over time, with overlapping hazard phases that include
544 climate shifts, food insecurity, and prolonged economic disruption, that may last long after the eruption
545 ends (Donovan & Oppenheimer, 2012; Newhall et al., 2018; Self, 2006). Advancing exposure assessments
546 to include cascading hazards and global climate interaction, and their effects on key systems is an essential
547 follow up from our study, in order to develop more regional and global preparedness strategies.

548 5.2 Dataset and methodological advancements

549 As highlighted in this study, a large-magnitude explosive eruption is still possible at a volcano that we know
550 little about. Burgos et al. (2022) report that since the start of the 20th century, 101 potentially active
551 volcanoes produced their first Holocene eruption. As studies continue to add detail to eruption histories,
552 more volcanoes with the potential for large-magnitude explosive eruptions may be identified and added to
553 our dataset.

554 There are inherent uncertainties with the exposure datasets used in our study. Herfort et al. (2023) highlight
555 the data incompleteness of OSM data, for instance, completeness is less than 20% for 9,163 cities globally.
556 This is reflected in the fact that Italy and Japan scored highly for infrastructure exposure compared to the
557 other countries (Figure 3). If we used different exposure datasets, numbers would likely vary due to levels
558 of completeness, different resolutions, and the type of exposure it is capturing (Table 6). This means that
559 the current exposure datasets result in under- or over-estimated exposures. However, improvements in the
560 resolution, completeness, and accuracy of exposure datasets will improve our results.

561 **Table 6:** Comparison of 2020 CE populations within 100 km of VEI 7 potential volcanoes globally for different population
562 datasets.

Population dataset	Resolution	Concept	Population <100 km
Global Human Settlement Layer – Population (GHS-POP)	100 m	Resident population	312,197,500 (this study)
LandScan Global Population	1 km	Ambient population (24-hour average)	315,077,725

WorldPop	100 m	Population distribution	316,755,371
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563

564 In our study we use the conservative distance of 100 km as the potential extent of PDC coverage, and use
565 the isopach footprints of the extent and thickness of the final tephra deposit to identify the worst-case
566 scenario. However, these eruptions are typically multi-phase, meaning different amounts of material are
567 ejected across days to years. For a more detailed analysis, where there are available isopachs, exposure can
568 be calculated at each stage of the eruption and integrated with dynamic evacuation plans. Hazard modelling
569 (e.g., time-dependent tephra dispersal: Costa et al. 2014), and regional or global climate modelling, can help
570 define likely VEI 7 eruption scenarios, including their duration and unrest, to support emergency managers,
571 similar to how NASA’s asteroid-impact exercises use modelled scenarios to test response plans (NASA
572 Planetary Defense Coordination Office (PDCO), 2024).

573 While exposure density is a key driver, the vulnerability of these communities is equally important. Certain
574 populations, such as the elderly, children, or tourists, face specific vulnerabilities and evacuation challenges
575 that are not reflected in aggregate population data. Particularly as, many of these VEI 7 candidate volcanoes
576 are in tourist or cultural sites, where an eruption could endanger visitors and damage heritage assets. Such
577 losses would extend to long-term effects on cultural capital and tourism, and affect critical nodes such as
578 airports, or ports (Mani et al., 2024). Also, exposure is not static, urban areas are expanding rapidly in many
579 regions, often encroaching into high-risk zones (Rentschler et al., 2022). Future exposure assessments could
580 move beyond simple counts of people and assets because such figures do not capture the dynamic and
581 heterogeneous nature of risk, but also the vulnerability and spatio-temporal changes of populations, critical
582 systems, buildings, and cropland. We can also integrate vulnerability of the exposed assets by applying
583 available fragility functions in order to forecast impacts of the eruptions.

584 6 Conclusions

585 This study provides a systematic assessment of direct exposure to potential large-magnitude explosive
586 eruptions, providing critical insights into the impacts of high-impact low-probability events, often ignored
587 or overlooked in favour of more likely events in risk assessments. Our approach offers an alternative to
588 probabilistic hazard mapping, which is currently unfeasible for these events due to sparse data availability.

589 We compiled a dataset of 136 volcanoes with the potential for a future VEI 7 eruption, with the majority
590 located in East and Southeast Asia. We show that approximately 312 million people live within 100 km of
591 a *VEI 7 potential volcano*. By quantifying exposure of population, infrastructure, and buildings, as well as area
592 of cropland, we highlight Laguna Caldera and Taal volcano in the Philippines, and Wilis volcano in
593 Indonesia, as those ranked with the highest exposures within 100 km of the volcanoes. This 100 km
594 represents the area of caldera collapse and PDC extent, with likely destruction and total loss of exposed
595 assets.

596 We show that exposure to these eruptions extends beyond 100 km, with damaging tephra fall extending
597 beyond this distance. We reconstruct a set of five tephra fall scenarios using past final VEI 7 tephra isopachs
598 to demonstrate how exposure varies with wind direction and isopach area. We show that exposure is
599 sensitive to isopach area and direction, particularly if the isopach encompasses a large urban or agricultural
600 area. We showed how exposure can increase or decrease with future wind directions. For example, if the
601 Ilopango eruption occurred today with the same wind directions and footprint as at the time of eruption,
602 ~ 1,575 years ago, 70.1 million people would be exposed, however if the tephra followed current wind
603 conditions, ~115 million people would be exposed, rising to ~131 million in the direction of future wind
604 conditions. Even thin ash deposits can cause agricultural loss or building damage, and affect infrastructure,
605 suggesting that exposure and risk assessment should extend beyond the typical 100 km buffers for these
606 large-scale events.

607 While the likelihood of a VEI 7 eruption in a given year remains low, the potential effects, both direct and
608 cascading, can cross national boundaries, and have global effects. Preparing for such events requires an
609 integration with societal vulnerability and adaptive communication strategies, as explored in this study. This
610 research supports that effort by identifying key exposure hotspots, in order to inform land-use and prioritise
611 preparedness planning, and highlights the importance of including high-impact low-probability events in
612 risk assessment to start to build resilience to extreme events.

613 7 Code Availability

614 Google Earth Engine was used to calculate land-use and building exposure. R was used to compile and
615 analyse the exposures. The code used in this manuscript is available at:
616 <https://github.com/elinorsmeredith/VolcExposure>.

617 8 Data Availability

618 Free and open access exposure data used are listed in the reference list. Ranking of volcanoes with the
619 potential of large-magnitude explosive eruptions, based on exposure to populations and physical assets is
620 provided in Supplementary Material.

621 9 Author Contribution

622 E.S.M. conceptualised the study with input from H.H. E.S.M. developed the methodology, collected and
623 curated the data, performed the analysis, wrote the code, made visualisations, and wrote the manuscript
624 draft. Wind data were provided by S.F.J. and M.M.C. M.M.C. produced the wind direction rings in Figure
625 7. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

626 10 Competing Interests

627 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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635 Supplementary Material

636

637 **S1:** Population exposure as a function of tephra deposit area for five VEI 7 eruption scenarios. Each point represents
 638 the population and area exposed at or above a given tephra thickness. The colours indicate tephra deposit
 639 thickness and shapes represent each volcanoes. In general, thinner, distal deposits affect larger areas and expose
 640 more people, while thicker, proximal deposits impact fewer people. Note the y-axis is

641 **S2:** Pressure levels corresponding to the 56 – 84% plume height used in the wind data collection.

Eruption	Maximum Plume Height (km)	Pressure levels
1815 Tambora, Indonesia	43 (above the volcano)	20 hPa – 1 hPa
946 Changbaishan, China	~25	150 hPa – 30 hPa
450 Ilopango, El Salvador	31	70 hPa – 10 hPa
10672 BP Fisher, USA	22	200 hPa – 70 hPa
1257 Rinjani, Indonesia	43	40 hPa – 6 hPa

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